

TUTORIAL ABOUT JADE AND JAMDER INSTALATION

PREPARATION

Required:

1. Windows 10
2. Eclipse IDE for Java EE Developers

Attention: When downloading the Eclipse installation file, other versions of the program may be displayed, be sure to install the Eclipse IDE for Java Developers version.

The tool will be used to CODE and not to MODEL, if another version of the program is installed, the following steps will not work.

3. Jade - JAVA Agent Development Framework
 - (1) Access the JADE website: <https://jade.tilab.com/>
 - (2) On the home page, position the cursor over “Download” and click in “Jade”.

Figura 1 – JADE home page

- (3) Accept the terms and click in jadeAll

Figure 2 – JADE download page

JADE	~ File size	Description of the content
jadeAll	17.7 MB	This file contains all JADE, i.e. it is just composed of the 4 files below. If it is too large for downloading, the 4 files below might be downloaded instead.
jadeBin	2.5 MB	This file contains JADE already compiled and ready to be used, i.e. a set of JAVA archive JAR files.
jadeDoc	12.8 MB	This file contains all the JADE documentation included the Administrator's Guide and the Programmer's Guide. NOTICE THAT all the documentation is also available on-line.
jadeSrc	2.3 MB	This file contains all the JADE source code.
jadeExamples	490 KB	This file contains the source code of the examples and a simple demo. All the examples and demo must be compiled.

(4) After downloading JADE, you will need JAMDER. JAMDER is available to download at: <https://github.com/rendleyarnou/tcc-ii-psmarcs/tree/main/Documentos/6.%20Desenvolver%20sistema%20multiagente%20com%20JAMDER/plugins>

(5) Save JAMDER in a folder on your computer.

Figure 3 - JAMDER, JADE and Eclipse folders

Nome	Tipo	Tamanho
jamder.jar	Arquivo do WinRAR	37 KB
JADE-all-4.5.0.zip	Arquivo ZIP do WinRAR	17.748 KB
eclipse-inst-win64.exe	Aplicativo	53.680 KB

INSTALATION

1. After finishing the Eclipse installation process, with the program running, create a new Java project: File -> New -> Java Project

Figure 4 – Starting a Java Project

2. After creating the project, you need to import JADE-all-*.zip. Click with the right button on the Project name and select “Properties”;

Figure 5 - Selecting Properties on Eclipse

3. Next, you should select Java Build Path -> Libraries -> Classpath -> Add External JARs

Figure 6 – Adding external JAR

4. You should select JADE-all-*.zip. Similar steps should be performed to add jamder.jar.

Figure 7 – JAMDER added to the Eclipse properties

Fonte: Elaborada pelo autor.

5. Next, you should select Apply and Close.
 - a. After following these steps, JADE and JAMDER plugins will appear as Referenced Libraries

Figure 8 - JADE and JAMDER plugins

Fonte: Elaborada pelo autor.